

Search for Potential Amoebicides. Part VII. Synthesis of Some Newer Piperazino Derivatives

VINAY S. MISRA and VIRENDRA K. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007 (INDIA)

Manuscript received 15 September 1976, revised 29 August 1977, revised 1 February 1978

A series of hydrazones of 1-[(4-methyl piperazino)-2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2-acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane has been synthesised by the condensation of 1-[(4-methyl piperazino)-2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2-acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane with various carbonyl compounds as potential amoebicides. Out of the total number of compounds synthesised, fifteen were tested against the axenic culture of *B. histolytica* at a conc. of 125 µg/ml but no significant amoebicidal activity was observed.

A large number of hydrazones of piperazine salts show promising amoebicidal activity¹⁻³. Recently some other hydrazones having good activity against *E. coli* have also been reported²⁻⁴. In continuation of our studies on piperazines as potential amoebicides⁵, we report here the preparation of several hydrazones of 1-[(4-methyl piperazino)-2-(4-nitrophenyl)-2-acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane (Table 1), expecting an increased anti-amoebic potency amongst these derivatives. Thus seventeen hydrazones were synthesised, 14 hydrazones and hydrazide (IV) tested for their amoebicidal activities against *E. histolytica*. However, these failed to show any significant activity when tested *in vitro*.

The synthesis of these compounds involves the following routes.

Experimental

ω -(4'-methyl piperazino)-4-nitro acetophenone (I)

N-Methyl piperazine (5 ml, 0.05 mole) and *p*-nitro phenacyl bromide (7 gm, 0.03 mole)* were refluxed in the presence of water for 15 hours. The resultant homogenous solution was then concentrated and cooled. The solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield 6 gm (50%), m.p. 138°

Found N 15.82% ; C₁₈H₁₇O₃N₃ ; Calc. N, 15.96%
C 59.31% ; C₁₈H₁₇O₃N₃ ; Calc. C, 59.46%
H 6.44% ; C₁₈H₁₇O₃N₃ ; Calc. H, 6.86%.

The I. R. spectra shows >C=O group peak at 1700 cm⁻¹.

4'-methyl piperazino-1-methyl-4-nitro phenyl carbinal (II)

2 gm (0.05 mole) of sodium borohydride were gradually added to a methanolic solution of ω -(4'-methyl piperazino) 4-nitro acetophenone (13.0 gm, 0.05 mole) during the course of an hour and under vigorous stirring. The stirring was continued for another half an hour and then the solution poured into cold water. The separated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield 7 gm (50%), m.p. 176°

Found N, 15.76% ; C₁₈H₁₉O₃N₃ ; Calc. N, 15.84%
C, 58.85% ; C₁₈H₁₉O₃N₃ ; Calc. C, 58.62%
H, 7.19% ; C₁₈H₁₉O₃N₃ ; Calc. H, 7.32%

The I.R. spectra does not show a >C=O group peak at 1700 cm⁻¹, but show peaks at 3400 cm⁻¹ and 1650 cm⁻¹. These are due to the presence of a sec. alcoholic (-CHOH) group.

* *p*-Nitro phenacyl bromide has been prepared by adopting the method adopted for the preparation of phenacyl bromide⁶.

1-[(4-methyl piperazino) 2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2-carboethoxy methoxy] ethane (III)

4'-methyl piperazino-1-methyl-4-nitro phenyl carbinol (6.0 gm, 0.25 mole) and α -chloroethyl acetate (7 ml, 0.03 mole) were refluxed together in the presence of dry benzene for 10 hours. The solution was cooled after distilling off the excess of benzene and the solid thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield 5.0 gm (62%), m.p. 226°

Found N, 11.43%; $C_{17}H_{25}O_5N_3$; Calc. N, 11.96%
 C, 58.11%; $C_{17}H_{25}O_5N_3$; Calc. C, 58.36%
 H, 7.12%; $C_{17}H_{25}O_5N_3$; Calc. H, 7.10%

1-[(4-methyl piperazino)-2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2 acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane (IV)

Hydrazine hydrate [98%, (5 ml, 0.1 mole)] was added to a cold ethanolic solution of 1-[(4-methyl piperazino) 2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2-carboethoxymethoxy] ethane (5 gm, 0.025 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 4 hours. The solution was then concentrated and cooled. The separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol.

Yield 3.0 gm (66%), m.p. 250°

Found N, 20.88%; $C_{15}H_{23}N_5O_4$; Calc. N, 20.79%
 C, 53.41%; $C_{15}H_{23}N_5O_4$; Calc. C, 53.32%
 H, 6.82%; $C_{15}H_{23}N_5O_4$; Calc. H, 6.72%

TABLE I

S. No.	R ₁	R ₂	% Yield	M.P., °C*	Mol. Formula	%N		%C		%H	
						Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1.	-H	-o-chloro phenyl	60	175	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ Cl	14.61	14.26	57.39	57.56	5.65	5.52
2.	-H	-p-chloro phenyl	62	196	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ Cl	14.61	14.46	57.39	57.42	5.65	5.42
3.	-H	-o-hydroxy phenyl	45	225	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₅	15.87	15.21	60.00	59.64	6.13	6.36
4.	-H	phenyl	50	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₅	16.47	16.75	62.11	62.86	6.34	6.24
5.	-H	-4-hydroxy 3-methoxy phenyl	54	180	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	14.85	15.63	60.00	59.58	6.30	6.36
6.	-H	-m-nitro phenyl	58	168	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅	17.87	17.64	56.17	56.40	5.53	5.72
7.	-H	-p-amino phenyl	60	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅	20.00	19.46	60.00	60.26	6.36	6.40
8.	-H	-styryl	65	165	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₅	15.52	14.57	64.00	64.02	6.44	6.40
9.	-H	-p-hydroxy phenyl	70	230	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₅	15.87	15.62	60.00	60.58	6.13	6.56
10.	-H	9-anthranenyl	62	200	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅	13.03	12.86	69.27	70.02	5.77	5.60
11.	-H	3-indolyl	55	220	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₅	18.14	17.94	64.45	64.96	6.13	5.98
12.	-H	-m-chloro phenyl	42	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₅ Cl	14.61	14.72	57.39	57.40	5.65	5.50
13.	-CH ₃	phenyl	50	110	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅	15.94	15.27	62.72	62.60	6.59	6.50
14.	-phenyl	phenyl	56	120	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₅	13.97	13.31	67.20	67.46	6.18	6.00
15.	-CH ₃	-p-hydroxy phenyl	60	192	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	15.38	15.83	60.65	60.12	6.37	6.40
16.	-CH ₃	-p-methoxy phenyl	54	198	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅	14.91	14.08	61.27	61.56	6.60	6.50
17.	-CH ₃	-p-nitro phenyl	65	180	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₅	17.35	17.01	57.02	57.00	5.78	6.50

* all the m.p. 's are uncorrected

Hydrazones of 1-[(4-methyl piperazino)-2-(4-nitro phenyl)-2-acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane (Table 1)

1-[(4-methyl piperazino) 2-(4-nitro phenyl) 2-acetyl hydrazido-oxy] ethane (0.05 mole) and an appropriate aldehyde or ketone (.05 mole) were taken in ethanol and the whole mass refluxed for 4 hours. The excess of the solvent was distilled off and the residue cooled, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Bioassay

Fifteen compounds [(IV) and 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11, 13,14,16 and 17 from Table 1)] were tested for their amoebicidal activity against the axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 125 µg/ml, but no significant amoebicidal activity observed.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. N. K. Prasad, Scientist 'B', Microbiology Division, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for the bioassay work and to Dr. S. K. Agarwal,

Research Associate, Department of Chemistry, I. I. T., Kanpur for the elemental analysis. The authors are also thankful to the Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for providing the necessary research facilities. One of them (VKS) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Post-doctoral Fellowship.

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